

SPECIAL ISSUE: The Wicked Problems in the Governance of the Just Green Transitions:
Between Territorial Resilience and Foresight

Resilient communities and the Just Green Transition: Towards adaptive and inclusive governance

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Abstract

Resilience has gained prominence as a governance paradigm in addressing the sociological uncertainties inherent in just green transitions. Thus, offering a framework for navigating the complexities, disruptions, and interdependencies that characterise the shift toward sustainable and equitable systems. This article investigates how governance mechanisms can be used to support adaptive and inclusive responses to challenges of green transition across diverse community contexts. Using a systematic literature review of 170 papers from 2015-2025, a complementary case study analysis, and 19 in-depth interviews, the study identifies governance mechanisms for transitions of resilience and justice. The paper addresses a critical question: How can resilient governance mechanisms be designed and implemented across diverse community contexts to support successful transformation processes? The findings indicate that participatory governance, including other forms of arrangements such as decentralised institutional arrangements, occurs across successful transition cases. The paper presents policy recommendations for policymakers, institutions, and community leaders seeking to navigate the complexities of the green transition while strengthening social cohesion. It concludes by proposing a resilience-based governance framework focused on distributive justice and human rights, contributing to more just and sustainable green transition trajectories.

Keywords

Inclusive responses; Community resilience; Just Green Transitions; Resilient governance

Introduction

The sudden urgency of climate action has driven societies toward the critical need for green transitions, thus reshaping economies, social structures, and governance systems. While these transformations lead to planetary sustainability, they also bring about uncertainties and

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implications that often challenge traditional policy-making and development (Rockström, 2015). Economic systems, jobs, and social structures are often disrupted, making it more difficult for governments and policymakers to rely on conventional practices and approaches to creating fair and effective solutions.

The concept of Just Green Transition (JGT) has emerged as a critical framework for ensuring that the shift toward low-carbon economies does not exacerbate existing inequalities or create new forms of social exclusion (Heffron, 2021). As countries reduce their reliance on fossil fuels and transition to renewable energy, there is a need for policies that protect vulnerable communities during this shift, ensuring environmental and social fairness (Heffron & McCauley, 2017). Significantly, inclusivity and equity have become major highlights in the just transition process. Governments and institutions often include diverse social groups, such as women, youth, communities, and marginalised groups, in decision-making processes to develop policies that reflect society's needs and perspectives. This approach helps avoid reinforcing existing risks, creating new divides, and ensures a sustainable and inclusive low-carbon future (Heffron, 2021; Newell & Mulvaney, 2013).

Central to the JGT discourse is the inherently disruptive process of transitioning, which creates both winners and losers across different boards and sectors (Ciplet, 2022; McLlroy, Brennan, & Barry, 2022). While there is potential for a just transition to benefit society, there is also a risk of disruption that can negatively impact, especially marginalised and vulnerable communities. For instance, as mines get shut down, coal mining communities are faced with economic devastation and environmental damage while urban areas benefit from clean energy investments. Also, indigenous communities are often faced with threats to losing their lands due to renewable energy projects, while some rich and affluent communities benefit from reduced fossil fuel use and improved air quality. These distributional impacts underscore the need for governance approaches and institutional strategies that can navigate complexity, adapt to changing circumstances and ensure inclusive outcomes.

Resilience ideologies provide a dynamic lens for understanding and managing transition dynamics (Abram et al., 2022; Ciplet, 2022). Originally developed in ecological systems research (Ungar, 2018), the concept has evolved into a multidisciplinary ideology encompassing social, economic and institutional dimensions (Flaherty, Flaherty & Ballard, 2019; Folke, 2006). However, in the context of green transitions, resilience ideologies provide a framework for understanding how communities withstand shocks, adapt to changing conditions, transform, and transition into more sustainable and equitable configurations (Reyers et al., 2022). For instance, the Ruhr region in Germany, which was formerly heavily dependent on coal mining, has gradually transformed into a more diversified and sustainable economic region as a result of

targeted investments in education, innovation, and renewable energy (Oei, Brauers, & Herpich, 2020).

Applying resilience ideologies to JGT remains unexplored, particularly in relation to governance mechanisms that promote adaptability and inclusivity at the community level (Radtke, 2025). While extensive literature exists on both resilience and JGT separately, there is a limited understanding of how these concepts intersect to inform governance practices and policies that can simultaneously address sustainability. Thus, recognising that equity, which goes beyond social inclusion and fairness, constitutes a dimension of sustainability rather than a separate objective (Gupta & Vegelin, 2016). This aligns with the Sustainable Development Goals (Gupta & Vegelin, 2016) but also the governance gaps this integration presents (Radtke, 2025). This gap calls for an in-depth examination of institutional and governance approaches to integrate and operationalise resilience in inclusive ways. Consequently, while resilience ideology promotes systems' adaptability, it lacks explicit attention to power relations, social justice, and equity (Matin, Forrester, & Ensor, 2018; Schmidt, 2015), which are major factors in the JGT.

This paper addresses the question: How can resilient governance mechanisms be designed and implemented across diverse community contexts to enhance adaptive and inclusive responses to transition-related challenges? Using a systematic literature review and case study analysis, the paper identifies the enabling conditions, mechanisms, and frameworks necessary for building community resilience that supports and promotes JGT. The paper contributes to the literature by developing an integrative theoretical framework that links community resilience with the JGT principles, thereby promoting an understanding of how these concepts mutually reinforce each other. It also identifies governance mechanisms and institutional strategies that promote adaptive and inclusive responses to transition challenges across different community contexts. Lastly, the paper offers practical policy recommendations for implementing resilience-based governance approaches that can enhance the justice dimensions of green transitions.

The analysis reveals that effective and successful resilience-based governance for JGT requires the following: (i) participatory planning processes that meaningfully engage diverse community stakeholders; (ii) institutional strategies that are decentralised to enhance local adaptation; (iii) continuous learning processes that facilitate adaptive management; (iv) distributive justice principles that ensure equitable access to transition benefits and protection from negative impacts; (v) recognition of diverse knowledge systems and values in transition planning.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides the theoretical framework for linking resilience thinking and JGT, and Section 3 presents the study's methodology, including the case study analysis. Section 4 presents the findings and synthesises these into a critical framework.

Section 5 concludes with practical and policy recommendations, as well as suggestions for further research.

Conceptual Framework

Understanding the JGT

The concept of just transitions emerged from labour movement advocacy for workers in declining fossil fuel industries, emphasising the need to protect employment and communities affected by the shift toward sustainable economies (Ghaleigh, 2019; Normann & Tellmann, 2021). In recent times, scholarships on just transition have expanded considerably beyond the broader questions of environmental and social justice (Hughes & Hoffmann, 2020; McCauley & Heffron, 2018). For example, contemporary scholars acknowledge the multiple dimensions of justice in green transitions (Gürtler, 2023; Stevis & Felli, 2016), which include the distributive scholarship (Hughes & Hoffmann, 2020; Gürtler, 2023; Newell, et al., 2021) addressing the fair allocation of costs and benefits (Newell, et al., 2021); the procedural justice that deals with participation in decision-making processes (Ryder, 2018; Suboticki, Heidenreich, Ryghaug, & Skjølsvold, 2023; Walker, et al., 2023); recognition justice, which is the acknowledgement of diverse identities and knowledge-based systems (Gürtler, 2023; Pandey & Sharma, 2021; San Martin & Wood, 2022); and the restorative justice scholarship, which addresses historical injustices (Hazrati & Heffron, 2021, 2024; De Haan & Destrooper, 2021).

The JGT depicts an evolution of thought that integrates environmental sustainability with the concept of social equity (Filipović, Lior & Radovanović, 2022; McCauley & Heffron, 2018; Sabato & Fronteddu, 2020; Shaker & Berisha, 2025). Its frameworks recognise and push for sustainability and justice, not as competing priorities, but rather as mutually reinforced objectives that require integrated approaches (Filipović, Lior & Radovanović, 2022; Sabato & Fronteddu, 2020). This ideology acknowledges that environmental degradation disproportionately affects vulnerable and marginalised populations while emphasising that sustainable solutions must address underlying inequalities to be effective and legitimate (Martin et al., 2020; Velicu & Barca, 2020).

Significantly, literature on JGT identifies key factors that should guide transition processes. Some of these factors are participation, inclusion, equity, and sustainability, amongst others. Participation emphasises the meaningful involvement of marginalised and affected communities in decision-making processes to ensure that transition processes are not forced or imposed by higher hierarchies, but are shaped through democratic deliberation (Boss et al., 2023; Radtke, 2025). Inclusion focuses on ensuring that marginalised communities are not left behind and that there is equal access to transition opportunities and benefits (Green & Gambhir, 2020; Middlemiss et al., 2023). Equity addresses both the distribution of transition costs and

benefits, as well as the processes through which these distributions are determined (Filipović, Lior & Radovanović, 2022; Green & Gambhir, 2020). Finally, sustainability pushes for transition pathways that address long-term environmental challenges while maintaining socioeconomic viability (Filipović, Lior & Radovanović, 2022; Green & Gambhir, 2020; Sabato & Fronteddu, 2020).

Community resilience

The concept of resilience thinking has progressed from its origins in ecological systems to encompass social-ecological systems that integrate human and natural components (Folke, 2016; Schoon & Van Der Leeuw, 2015). Resilience thinking seeks to govern socio-ecological dynamics for enhanced human well-being at both local and global levels (Folke, 2016). It demonstrates the ability of people, societies, and cultures to thrive and develop, navigating complexity, uncertainty, and change in an environment (Grove, 2018). Therefore, for resilience to thrive, people must have the capacity to continue learning, self-organise, and grow in environments faced with uncertainty and instability (Joseph & McGregor, 2019).

Community resilience encompasses multiple interrelated dimensions (Matarrita-Cascante et al., 2017). These are the adaptive capacity, transformative capacity, social cohesion, and institutional capacity. Adaptive capacity refers to the ability to adjust to changing conditions through learning, experimentation, and innovation (Allen & Holling, 2010). Transformative capacity refers to the ability to create significant new systems when existing arrangements become untenable (Maurischa, Fahm, & Abi Suroso, 2023; Wolfram, Borgstrom, & Farrelly, 2019). Social cohesion goes beyond networking, relationships, and shared values that enable collective action (Aldrich, 2017; Pfefferbaum, Van Horn, & Pfefferbaum, 2017). Lastly, institutional capacity includes the formal and informal rules, organisations, and governance arrangements that coordinate community responses (Poland et al., 2021).

The literature on the resilience school of thought emphasises key elements of resilient systems, including diversity, modularity and redundancy, adaptive learning, and cross-scale linkages (Mendizabal et al., 2018; Sze, 2017). Diversity in terms of economic activities, social groups, and institutional arrangements provides diverse pathways for responding to challenges and reduces vulnerability to specific shocks (Sze, 2017). Modularity and redundancy ensure that system failures in one area do not cascade throughout the entire system (Ruhl, 2019; Shariff, 2023). Adaptive learning enables systems to adjust their strategies based on experience and changing conditions (Mendizabal et al., 2018; Ruiz-Mallén, 2022). Finally, cross-scale linkages connect local communities with regional and global networks that provide resources and support (Rockenbauch & Sakdapolrak, 2017).

Integrating resilience thinking and JGT

Integrating the resilience school of thought and JGT often presents a strategy for addressing both sustainability and equity challenges (Sze & Yaempierre, 2017). In such cases, integration recognises that green transitions are complex, non-linear processes that produce both opportunities and risks for communities (Abram et al., 2022; Swilling, 2019). Thus, requiring adaptive governance approaches that can navigate uncertainty while ensuring inclusive outcomes (Mendizabel et al., 2018; Pearson & Bardsley, 2022).

Significantly, resilience-informed JGT emphasises several key principles. These are adaptive inclusion, transformative justice, anticipatory governance and multi-scale coordination (McElduff et al., 2016). Adaptive inclusivity ensures that participation mechanisms can evolve as transitions occur and new stakeholders emerge (Radtke, 2025). Transformative justice recognises that achieving sustainability may require certain fundamental changes to existing socioeconomic arrangements; however, the changes must address rather than increase existing inequalities (Bennett et al., 2019; Martin et al., 2020). While anticipatory governance develops the capacity to identify and respond to challenges before they escalate into crises (Mendizabel et al., 2018), multi-scale coordination ensures that local adaptations are supported by and contribute to the broader transition objectives (Swarnaker & Singh, 2022).

The integrated approach explained above also emphasises the significance of learning and experimentation in transition processes (Mendizabel et al., 2018; Radtke, 2025). Resilience-informed JGT embraces uncertainty and complexity, rather than simply following predetermined pathways (Pearson & Bardsley, 2022). Thus, creating opportunities for communities to develop context-appropriate solutions through iterative processes of action and reflection (Pearson & Bardsley, 2022; Swarnaker & Singh, 2022). This approach recognises that different communities will face different challenges and possess different assets, thereby requiring diverse rather than standardised responses (Abram et al., 2022; Swilling, 2019).

This study builds on these insights to propose specific governance mechanisms that can enable adaptive and inclusive responses to transition challenges. These mechanisms are organised around five key dimensions, namely, participatory planning, decentralised governance, institutional learning, distributive justice, and knowledge integration. Table 1 below summarises the conceptual framework, presenting the key differences and the political contexts in which they operate. The table also shows that equity is a significant component of sustainability, not just a standalone issue.

Table 1: Conceptual framework, key differences and contexts

Concept	Primary focus	Major priority	Political context	Relationship to Justice
Sustainable Development	Longterm viability across environmental and socioeconomic dimensions	Balanced integration	UN SDGs framework	Equity is seen as core (SDGs 5, 10)
Sustainability	Based on ecological limits and generative capacity	Environmental and social	Political economies vary	Widely recognised as significant
Resilience	Presents the capacity to absorb shocks, adapt, and transform	System persistence	Often neoliberal	Often absent, may reinforce inequalities
Just Transition	Equity distribution of costs and/or benefits	Social justice	Labor or social democracy	Explicit and central
Green Transition	A shift toward low carbon economy	Environmental sustainability	Varied	Variable by approach

Source: Author's work adapted from scholarships such as Schmidt (2015), Stevis & Felli (2016), and Shaker & Berisha (2025)

Methodology

The study employed a systematic literature review (SLR) approach (Booth et al., 2021; Page et al., 2021), complemented by in-depth interviews and a comparative case study analysis. The review adheres to the guidelines and principles outlined in the Cochrane Handbook of Systematic Reviews of Interventions (Higgins, Deeks, & Altman, 2022) to ensure methodological rigour and consistency. It focuses on conceptual insights from peer-reviewed literature from 2015 to 2025. The search strategy involved academic databases including Scopus, Web of Science, Google Scholar, ScienceDirect, and SpringerLink. Combined search terms were used to examine the following key terms: resilience, green transitions, community governance, and environmental justice.

The 170 papers included in the review process were analysed using thematic synthesis. Titles and abstracts were screened against the inclusion and exclusion criteria; thereafter, full texts

were read and coded thematically around the five governance dimensions discussed in the findings. Search terms were organised and managed in four separate categories:

Table 2: Inclusion and exclusion criteria for literature sources on resilient communities and JGT

Source type	Description/Examples	Purpose/Rationale	Inclusion
Peer-reviewed journal articles	Empirical studies (both qualitative and quantitative research)	Examined evidence on theories, case studies and interventions	Inclusive
Case studies (e.g., ethnographies, participatory action)	Community-driven solutions, geographic location (global north context)	Practical, real-world examples	Inclusive
Books/book chapters	Theoretical foundations for resilient communities	Conceptual thoroughness and grinding	Inclusive
Policy documents	Government framework/policy for JGT	Conceptual thoroughness and grinding	Inclusive
Reports	Critical insights on policy implementation gaps, data and data bias, engagement strategies	Illuminate systemic enquiries and offer solid approaches to decision-making	Inclusive
Non-English studies	Publications done in other languages	Prevention due to resource limitations	Exclude
Editorials, commentaries, opinion pieces	Opinion essays, editorials, and others	Lack of empirical rigour	Exclude

Source: Author's compilation following the inclusion and exclusion criteria

Figure 1: PRISMA flow diagram outlining the article selection and screening process

Source: Author's own elaboration

Case study analysis

The study also employed purposive sampling for the case study component. Six cases were selected to showcase diverse communities, transition challenges, and governance strategies. These cases were selected to maximise variations across geographic regions, socioeconomic contexts, and the various transition changes present in each case. Cases selected include: (i) coal mining communities in Ruhr Valley, Germany responding to the closure of the mine; (ii) indigenous communities in northern Canada navigating the impacts of renewable energy development; (iii) fishing communities in Denmark adapting to offshore wind development; (iv) agricultural communities in Kenya for the implementation of climate-smart agriculture; (v) urban neighborhoods in Detroit, United States developing community energy systems; and (vi) island communities in the Pacific for the implementation of climate adaptation measures.

The cases were selected based on their relevance to one or more of the five governance dimensions identified through the SLR, as well as their geographic locations and socioeconomic distinctions. The cases ranged across the global North and South, all facing challenges in industrial, agricultural, and ecological transition.

Data collection for each case involved document analysis, including policy reports, planning documents, academic studies and reports, as well as media coverage. Some of these findings were also supported by interviews with key stakeholders, including government officials, community leaders, and representatives from civil society organisations. The data analysis aimed to identify patterns and variations in governance approaches to the JGT process.

In-depth Interviews

A total of 19 in-depth interviews were conducted between December 2024 and May 2025 across three out of the six case countries: Germany, Canada, and Denmark. While 7 of these were conducted in person with individuals from indigenous communities in Northern Canada from December 2024 to February 2025, the remaining in-depth interviews were conducted online through Zoom calls. Interviews were selected through a purposive sampling to ensure representation across different groups and perspectives. The in-depth interview underwent multiple rounds of reviews and refinement to ensure contextual relevance. Both the in-person and Zoom call interviews lasted 60 to 90 minutes each. The data were analysed using NVivo software, and codes were generated from themes that also emerged from the interviews.

Findings

The analysis reveals five key dimensions of resilience-based governance that enable adaptive and inclusive responses to the challenges of the green transition: (i) participatory planning and democratic deliberation, (ii) decentralised governance and subsidiarity, (iii) institutional learning and adaptive management, (iv) distributive justice and equity mechanisms, (v) knowledge integration and epistemological pluralism. Each dimension includes specific mechanisms and practices that contribute to building community resilience while advancing justice objectives. These are also structured into a simple novel framework that can guide and contribute toward building community resilience while promoting justice. This section will discuss each of the dimensions listed, providing examples from the case studies to complement the findings explained and present a model framework.

Participatory planning and democratic deliberation

Participatory planning emerges as a fundamental mechanism for ensuring that green transitions are inclusive and responsive to community needs and priorities. However, the study analysis reveals significant variations in how participation is conceptualised and implemented across different contexts, with major implications for both effectiveness and equity. Effective and useful participatory planning for JGT involves moving beyond consultation to active power-sharing and equity in decision-making processes.

The case of Germany's coal region transition demonstrates how meaningful and useful participation can be achieved through multi-stakeholder platforms that bring together government representatives, business leaders, labour unions, environmentalists, environmental groups, and community organisations. These groups operate through consensus-based decision-making processes to ensure that all stakeholders have meaningful input and influence over transition planning.

However, participation mechanisms must be designed to address power dynamics and imbalances, as well as ensure the voices of marginalised communities are heard. For example, the case of Indigenous communities in northern Canada demonstrates how 'standard consultation' processes tend to exclude Indigenous views and needs. This often leads to resistance, conflicts and unrest. For participatory planning to be an effective approach or mechanism, Indigenous sovereignty and self-determination must be recognised. More so, the right to free, prior and informed consent relates to developments that are affecting traditional territories.

Literature emphasises several design principles for inclusive participation. For instance, accessibility as a design principle ensures that participation opportunities are readily available to all communities, regardless of their educational background, literacy levels, language, or economic status. This may also involve the provision of childcare, translation services, transportation or compensation for time spent on planning activities. While transparency involves sharing information regarding transition plans, decision-making processes, and trade-offs in accessible formats, accountability mechanisms ensure that decisions are influenced by community input and the voices of community members.

Furthermore, deliberative approaches have proven particularly significant for navigating complex transition challenges. These deliberative approaches tend to create space and opportunities for learning and dialogue across various angles. For example, the Danish case of fishing communities and offshore wind development demonstrates how structured deliberations can help stakeholders understand different viewpoints and develop mutually

acceptable solutions. These examples, along with their processes, require the facilitation of skills and time to build trust and develop relationships.

Lastly, the digital arena and digital technologies offer new opportunities for expanding participation while also creating new challenges for inclusive engagement. Research on digital participation consistently shows that online platforms can enable broader engagement beyond time and geographic constraints (Afzalan & Muller, 2018; Falco & Kleinhans, 2018). However, community members who lack digital access or skills are often excluded from digital platforms. Hybrid approaches that combine face-to-face and online engagement prove, over time, to be most effective for maximising participation.

Decentralised governance and subsidiarity

Decentralised governance enables adaptive responses by solving problems locally while allowing a higher-level intervention when necessary (Brisbois, 2020). Therefore, it provides a framework for balancing local autonomy with system-wide coordination. The analysis reveals that effective decentralisation requires both formal institutional settings and informal networks and relationships. Formal arrangements include legal frameworks that allow local government authority over transition planning and implementation. It also allows for fiscal mechanisms that provide resources for local initiatives and accountability systems that ensure democratic oversight.

Informal networks extend beyond relationships between community leaders, knowledge-sharing mechanisms, and collaborative partnerships that foster collective action (Wanberg, Javernick & Taylor, 2017). In the case of Detroit, community-controlled energy systems arise through decentralised government arrangements, which occur to allow for neighbourhood-level innovation (Wu, Schiffer & Burns, 2016). Local ownership of renewable energy has been created through resident initiative. This action ultimately reduced energy costs for low-income households. For a successful outcome, communities will need supportive policies, access to technical assistance, and flexible regulatory frameworks that accommodate community-scale energy systems.

However, decentralisation can also bring about challenges for coordination and equity if not designed appropriately. Small local communities may lack the technical know-how or financial capacity to address complex transition challenges, thus requiring government support. The lack of coordinated, decentralised mechanisms may lead to conflicting initiatives that may ultimately undermine transition objectives.

Polycentric governance strategies that recognise multiple centers of authority at different levels offer a framework for addressing these issues (Carlisle & Gruby, 2019; Stephan, Marshall

& McGinnis, 2019). The case of the Pacific Island shows how climate adaptation can lead to effective coordination through a hub of institutional arrangements (Robinson & Gilfillan, 2017). These arrangements connect community adaptation initiatives with national and international climate policies and cooperation mechanisms, facilitating successful coordination (McNamara et al., 2020). However, the process requires clear role definitions, resource-sharing agreements, and coordination protocols that enable coherent action across all levels (Carlisle & Gruby, 2019; McNamara et al., 2020).

Capacity building emerged as a significant enabler of effective decentralisation. Therefore, local communities need technical, financial, and organisational capacity to increase responsibilities for transition planning and implementation. This includes organising training for community members and their local leaders, accessing expert advice, establishing peer learning networks, and implementing flexible funding mechanisms that support community initiatives.

Institutional learning and adaptive management

Green transitions require adaptive strategies and learning-based governance due to persistent complexities (Radtke, 2025). Significantly, institutional learning goes beyond both formal and informal processes through which organisations and communities acquire, process, and apply new knowledge to improve their performance and outcomes (Fuenfschilling, 2019).

The literature reveals several key components of institutional learning systems. For example, monitoring and evaluation mechanisms track progress toward transition goals while also identifying unintended and emerging challenges (Mendizabal, et al., 2018). Feedback systems ensure that monitoring information reaches decision makers and influences future planning (McAllister et al., 2019; Mendizabal et al., 2018). Experimentations and innovations bring the possibility of trying new approaches and promoting new innovative ideas (Pearson & Bardsley, 2022; Rockenbauch & Sakdapolrak, 2017). Moreover, knowledge management systems facilitate the attraction and sharing of lessons learned across various initiatives and contexts (Dóci, Rohracher, & Kordas, 2022; Hordijk & Baud, 2011; Suryawan & Lee, 2025).

In Kenya, climate-smart agriculture provides a framework that enables farmer field schools to establish institutional learning systems, facilitating continuous adaptation to changing climate conditions (Chesterman & Neely, 2015; Osumba, Recha, & Oroma, 2021). These schools organise forums where farmers, teachers, climate action advocates, researchers and others converge to experiment with new agricultural practices and share knowledge about what works within local contexts and conditions (Oja Da Silva, 2023; Osumba, Recha, & Oroma, 2021). In this case, success requires experimentation, knowledge sharing, and adaptive policy frameworks.

Often, institutional learning is hindered by barriers that necessitate effective governance mechanisms to become effective and successful (Sze & Yeampierre, 2017). Organisational cultures may resist change or avoid learning from mistakes. Moreover, political pressures for rapid results may hinder long-term learning investments, and resource constraints may limit the capacity for monitoring, evaluation, and experimentation activities.

Adaptive management frameworks provide structured approaches for institutionalising learning in complex situations (Pieraccini, 2019). These frameworks present recurring cycles of planning, implementation, monitoring, and adjustment, updating strategies based on experience (Mendizabal et al., 2018; O'Connell, Walker, Abel & Grigg, 2015). They require institutional mechanisms that support experimentation, protect learning activities from political interference, and ensure that lessons learned influence future decisions.

Distributive justice and equity mechanisms

The study analysis reveals that the equitable distribution of transition costs and benefits is imperative for building community support and resilience. Distributive justice addresses both the process by which decisions are made and the outcomes they produce. The study's analysis reveals multiple dimensions of distributional concerns related to green transitions. These include the economic, environmental, social, and cultural impacts.

The economic impacts include job losses in declining industries, new employment opportunities in emerging sectors, and changes in energy costs (Sze & Yeampierre, 2017). Other economic impacts include differential access to transition benefits such as energy efficiency programs or renewable energy investments. Environmental impacts encompass changes in air and water quality, noise levels, and the ecosystem services that may affect communities in different ways. The social and cultural impacts encompass changes in community cohesion, cultural practices, and social networks that result from economic and environmental changes (Camen et al., 2022).

Effective approaches to distributive justice require systematic attention to identifying and addressing distributional impacts throughout transition processes (Hughes & Hoffman, 2020; Stark, Gale & Murphy-Gregory, 2023). Subsequently, there are impact assessment mechanisms that analyse how communities and social groups are impacted by transition policies and investments. For instance, compensation programs provide resources for communities and individuals who bear the costs of transition. Investment targeting ensures that transition benefits reach marginalised and disadvantaged communities that have been historically excluded from economic opportunities (Green & Gambhir, 2020; Sze & Yeampierre, 2017).

The German coal transition case illustrates how critical distributive justice approaches can push political support for ambitious climate policies while protecting the interests of affected communities (Furnaro et al., 2021; Mundaca, Busch, & Schwer, 2018). The phase-out package for the government's coal includes a substantial amount of compensation for mining regions, retention programs for displaced workers, and targeted investments in new economic activities (Furnaro et al., 2021; Oei, Brauers, & Herpich, 2020). The success of this program requires a long-term commitment to the affected communities, transparent processes for determining compensation, and meaningful participation by affected stakeholders in the design process for the support programs (Radtke & David, 2024).

In addition to the success mentioned in the German coal transition case, in practice, the distributive justice approach generally faces significant challenges. For instance, defining a fair and just distribution entails value judgements on which impacts matter the most and how different types of costs and benefits should be weighted (Galanis, 2025). Furthermore, while resource constraints limit the ability to fully compensate for all negative impacts, political dynamics may favour well-organised interests over marginalised and disadvantaged communities.

Knowledge integration and epistemological pluralism

Green transitions encompass a range of knowledge systems, including scientific research, technical expertise, local ecological knowledge, traditional practices, and experiential learning (Hjerpe, Glaas, & Fenton, 2017). Effective governance needs mechanisms for integrating diverse knowledge systems while respecting different ways of knowing and understanding environmental and social challenges (Radtke, 2025).

The study analysis reveals that knowledge integration faces several challenges in practice (UI-Durar, 2023). Different knowledge systems may operate with varying assumptions, methodologies, and validation criteria (Hjerpe, Glaas, & Fenton, 2017). Certain types of knowledge may be privileged by power imbalances while marginalising others, and communication barriers may prevent effective knowledge sharing across different communities and contexts (Qureshi, Sutter & Bhatt, 2018).

Indigenous knowledge systems present significant contributions to transition planning. However, these groups are often marginalised in traditional policy processes (Lam et al., 2020). Traditional ecological knowledge provides an in-depth understanding of local environmental conditions and of sustainable resource management practices developed over generations (Hjerpe, Glaas, & Fenton, 2017; Lam et al., 2020). Indigenous governance systems offer models for decision-making that integrate social, economic, and spiritual considerations (McAllister,

2024). Consequently, cultural values and worldviews provide an alternative framework for understanding societal relationships (Campbell, Chanse & Schindler, 2024).

The case of renewable energy in Northern Canada presents both opportunities and challenges for integrating indigenous knowledge. Indigenous communities possess in-depth knowledge of local environmental conditions, wildlife patterns, and sustainable land-use practices that are essential for effective renewable energy siting and impact mitigation (Lam et al., 2020). However, traditional environmental assessment processes often fail to integrate this knowledge. This may lead to projects that impede significant cultural sites.

Toward a Resilience-based Governance Framework

The framework integrates the dimensions explained above. The dimensions are significant for building resilient communities through JGT, and each contributes to adaptive and inclusive governance that can respond to complex socioecological challenges while ensuring equity and participation. It also presents variations in how communities respond to green challenges, as explained in the discussion section above.

Figure 2: A Novel Framework for Resilience-Based Governance

Source: Author's own elaboration

A few key principles that are essential foundations for resilience-based governance of JGT. These are adaptive inclusivity, transformative justice, anticipatory learning, scalar coordination,

and epistemological pluralism. These principles move beyond reformist approaches to effective governance mechanisms that require flexible participation that accommodate meaningful civic engagement.

Conclusion

The paper examined the role of resilience thinking in enabling adaptive and inclusive governance for JGT. Through a systematic literature review, complemented by examples from case studies, the research identified key governance mechanisms, institutional arrangements, and enabling or supportive conditions that support community resilience while advancing sustainability and equity. The findings reveal that effective governance of JGT encompasses technocratic approaches. It is embedded in inclusive and adaptive approaches that recognise the complexities and uncertainties in the transition processes. Resilience thinking offers valuable insights into the development of such approaches; however, it must be integrated with justice considerations to ensure that it does not perpetuate existing inequalities.

The proposed framework presents five key dimensions of resilience-based governance. These are participatory planning and democratic deliberation, decentralised governance and subsidiarity, institutional learning and adaptive management, distributive justice and equity mechanisms, and knowledge integration and epistemological pluralism. Each dimension possesses specific mechanisms that contribute toward building community resilience while promoting justice objectives. Consequently, the framework provides a foundation for continued work on resilience-based governance of JGT. The study also presents enabling conditions that support resilience-based governance, including sociopolitical systems that spur democratic participation, economic resources for transition investments, social capital that facilitates collective action, institutional capacity for coordination and implementation, and cultural contexts that promote community cooperation and innovation.

Furthermore, the research contributes to the literature on community resilience and JGT. Theoretically, it promotes integration of resilience thinking with environmental and social justice frameworks. Thus, it presents new insights into how the concepts simultaneously reinforce each other. For practice, it offers actionable guidance for policymakers, community leaders, and other stakeholders seeking to navigate the complexities of green transitions while ensuring inclusive outcomes. In conclusion, as communities continue to face increasing pressures from climate change, economic disruption, and social inequality, there is a need for governance approaches and strategies that ensure inclusive outcomes.

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Conflict of interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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Author statement on the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools

I confirm that no artificial intelligence (AI) tools were used in the research, analysis, or writing of this manuscript. I also confirm that all references cited in the manuscript are genuine, have been consulted by the author(s), and are not fabricated or generated by AI.

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